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ACCOMPLISHMENT REPORT IN CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT PROJECT READ TO EXCEL ON ADVANCING DEVELOPMENT VERSION 2.0

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ABSTRACT

Proponent: MARIA CECILIA C. CLAVE

Reading is necessary for learning, so instilling a love of reading at an early age is the key that unlocks the door to lifelong learning. Instilling a love of reading early gives a child a head start on expanding their vocabulary and building independence and self-confidence.

DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019 "**HAMON: BAWAT BATA BUMABASA (3Bs Initiative)**", will help strengthen the "Every Child is a Reader Program" which primarily aims to equip the learners with reading skills to make them proficient and independent readers in their grade level. Jesus S. Cabarrus conducted Project READ Version 1 last SY 2018–2019, which resulted in to increase in the number of readers which indicates that the project was successful.

As shown in the Reading Progress Chart in Filipino last November 2022 on the pre-reading assessment conducted by all Grade 1 teachers, it was found that there were 114 out of 420 of the total enrollments are non-readers who need an immediate response. Due to this, pupils must practice reading with the help of their parents/guardians and teachers.

In line with this we conducted READ Version 2 in the leadership of our dear school principal Mrs. Evangeline R. Quibuyen and team leader Mrs. Maria Cecilia Clave who never gives up on various aspects of school programs and so much dedicated and passionate to share knowledge to improve the learners' reading skills. The Grade 1 advisers together with the whole team conducted limited face-to-face readings with parents' consent in school.

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FINDINGS

After an accurate analysis of data, we found out that from 114 non-readers, only 24 pupils were left as non-readers. This means that 79% (90 pupils) of the non-readers became readers after the implementation of the CI Project (READ) Version 2. It is indicated that the school had made an effective implementation plan in addressing the non-readers of grade one pupils.

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